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Ionospheric perturbations initiated due to the forest-fire over Greece as a consequence of lithosphere-atmosphere-ionosphere coupling

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ABSTRACT

A very devastating and long duration wildfire episode occurred in Greece near Athens during 20–25 July 2018. We have investigated particulate matter PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}; and selected greenhouse gases such as CO₂, NO₂, SO₂, and CH₄ which are known to be generated due to the burning of coal, vegetation, and gasoline. There are significant changes in carbon dioxide, methane and carbon monoxide based on the simulations with the chemical transport model. Further, we have checked the ionospheric perturbations during 20–25 July 2018, using the global positioning system (GPS) derived total electron content (TEC) maps over Greece. We have used detrended TEC data to observe the fluctuation in the ionospheric total electron during the presented event. We found that strong ionospheric perturbations have appeared during these events in coincident location to the lower atmospheric anomalies observed in the troposphere and stratosphere. A possible mechanism of the generation of the Atmospheric Gravity Waves (AGW) and Earth's surface-atmosphere-ionosphere coupling has been discussed. Detrended atmospheric gases/particulate matter density and detrended GPS TEC shows similar variation trend, however, ionospheric changes show significant time delay. This indicates the energy from forest fire region penetrates into ionosphere through the lower atmosphere and gradually triggers fluctuations in the density of the atmospheric elements as well as ionospheric TEC.

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1. Introduction

Wildfires are devastating incidents that can occur due to the lightning, tree to tree frictions, human activities, etc. They often result into the destruction of the unmovable properties and injuries or deaths to humans and animals. Wildfires can take place anywhere and at any time, but, mostly they begin in forests, grasslands or prairies.

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They can contaminate the atmosphere by adding loads of trace gases and aerosols into Earth's atmosphere. Consequently, forest fires significantly contribute to atmospheric air pollution and also cause significant reduction in the visibility during their occurrence and for several days thereafter. Due to the burning of biomass during the wildfire episodes, huge emission of the gases such as carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), particulate volatile and compounds arise (Lobert and Warnatz 1993; Strada et al. 2012). Following the atmospheric transport conditions, pollutants associated with the wildfires can travel large distances from regional scales to global scales (Takegawa et al. 2003; Miranda et al. 2008; Bytnerowicz et al. 2010; Strada et al. 2012). Certain meteorological conditions allow wildfire smoke plumes to disperse to a large distance which often causes contamination in the air at far distances from the wildfire location (Sapkota et al. 2005). The wildfire episodes are sporadic, transitory, highly variable in concentration, and can occur in dense forests at any time (Centre for Disease Control. 2014; Rappold et al. 2017).

Natural hazards such as volcanic eruptions, earthquakes, tsunamis, and tropospheric weather events as well as detonations of nuclear devices generate gravity as well as acoustic waves in the atmosphere. Often during such natural hazards atmospheric as well as ionospheric perturbations are caused by the upward propagation of these waves. Many recent research investigations have demonstrated numerous ways to localize the regions of natural hazards by detecting the ionospheric signatures associated with these natural hazards (Astafyeva 2019; Meng et al. 2019; Huang et al. 2019). Atmospheric Gravity Waves (AGWs) are normal atmospheric waves and in the lower atmosphere, they are often triggered by natural hazards such as forest fires, volcanoes, earthquakes, hurricanes, etc. due to the variations in the electron density and plasma of Earth's gas envelope. These AGWs cause the energy exchange coupling Earth's surface-atmosphere-ionosphere by transporting Earth's gas envelope electron density and plasma perturbation from the tropospheric to the thermospheric heights. These waves can travel large horizontal as well as vertical distances with minimal attenuation. AGWs in the ionosphere or the upper atmosphere are termed as traveling ionospheric disturbances (TIDs) and they are responsible for the exchange of energy and momentum from the neutral atmosphere (troposphere-mesosphere-stratosphere) to the upper ionized atmosphere (Ionosphere). If the TIDs are triggered by the neutral atmosphere due to the natural hazards or strong anthropogenic activity (e.g., rocket launch, vegetation burning, etc.) they will reflect quite similar density fluctuation as in the neutral atmosphere (Belehaki et al. 2017; Fedorenko et al. 2013; Hines 1974; Hocke and Schlegel 1996; Priyadarshi et al. 2018 and references therein). Once they arrive at the ionospheric heights they can cause up to 10% more fluctuation in the ionospheric TEC and electron density which is significant enough to cause perturbation in trans-ionospheric radio wave communication and ranging systems (Priyadarshi et al. 2011a, 2011b, Davies 1990; Mcnamara 1991).

In the presented paper we are studying a forest fire episode that occurred during 20-25 July 2018 in Greece and caused a huge loss of human lives and property. During this event, a large amount of trace gases have been transported into the atmosphere. We are studying the anomalies in the different Earth's atmospheric layers

from the troposphere to the ionosphere. For this, we are studying the CO, CO₂, Methane and other trace gases concentration in the lower atmosphere and investigating the traces of TIDs triggered due to this wildfire episode over Greece. In the next section, we would introduce the methodology and data that we are using in this paper to study the wildfire event episode. In the results and discussion section we will present the atmospheric anomaly results that we found at the different heights of Earth's atmosphere. The causes of the anomalies have been discussed in two ways. At first, we have demonstrated them by data illustration, but in some places due to lack of observations we have used previously published works to discuss the possible anomalies caused in the atmospheric layers. In the last part of our manuscript, we have summarized important outcomes of the presented atmospheric traces of the Greece wildfire investigation and also discussed our future research plans in line with the presented research work.

2. Data and methodology

2.1. GPS TEC data from the madrigal database

The ionospheric total electron content (TEC) has been obtained from the Madrigal database (<http://millstonehill.haystack.mit.edu/>). Madrigal database is the upper atmospheric database used by the several space weather research groups throughout the world. Madrigal datasets (several upper atmosphere related instruments and space weather-related models) are available in archival real-time in several formats and these data sets are uploaded and controlled locally. It is possible to search all worldwide data available through madrigal as these local data providers can be searched from any location and on any madrigal website. We are using the worldwide GPS TEC 1 minute data available at the Madrigal database.

2.2. Method of TEC fluctuation calculation

For the TEC fluctuations estimations, we have used GPS receiver processes TEC data and detrended it for 1° geographic latitude and 1° geographic longitude (Priyadarshi et al. 2018). For detrending, we have used MATLAB detrending subroutine. MATLAB detrending function subtracts the mean or a best-fit line from the data and this will allow us to see systematic fluctuation and increase and decrease in data. TEC fluctuations are calculated using the following formula:

$$TEC \text{ Fluctuation } (lat, lon) = \sum_{i=30}^{i=45} \sum_{j=15}^{j=30} \text{Mean Detrended TEC} * N_{i,4}(lat) * M_{j,4}(lon) \quad (1)$$

In Eq(1) input detrended data have been averaged for every 1° geographic latitude and 1° geographic longitude. $N_{i,4}$ is the degree 4 B-spline basis function for the latitude where i varies from 30-45°; and $M_{j,4}$ is degree 4 B-spline basis function for the longitude where j varies from 15-30°. In this way the binned detrended TEC data

is projected on the univariate B-spline basis functions $N_{i,4}$ and $M_{j,4}$. B-spline techniques are best for such TEC fluctuation studies as they preserve the local trend of the data and avoid any sudden fluctuations (e.g., Priyadarshi et al. 2018; Priyadarshi and Wernik 2014; Priyadarshi 2015; Priyadarshi et al. 2016). Due to the projecting the detrended TEC data on the two univariate B-spline basis functions along the latitude and longitude, the data visualization is enhanced by $1/10^{\text{th}}$ in latitude as well as in the longitude.

2.3. Simulations with the chemical transport model

We have used the Weather Research and Forecasting model with Chemistry (WRF-Chem) to provide spatial and temporal distribution of air pollutants over Greece. WRF-Chem is an online model as the chemistry and meteorological components are fully coupled (Fast et al., 2006; Grell et al., 2005). Both components use the same transport scheme, horizontal and vertical grid, time step, and physical parameterizations for subgrid-scale transport. The model has several choices for gas-phase chemical mechanisms, photolysis processes, and aerosol schemes.

The model domain covered Europe with 12 km x 12 km grid and 35 vertical levels. The model configuration includes the Noah Land Surface Model (Chen and Dudhia 2001), YSU boundary layer physics (Hong et al. 2006), RRTMG long and short wave radiation scheme (Iacono et al. 2008), Grell 3 D parameterization with radiation feedback and shallow convection, Morrison 2-moments microphysics scheme (Morrison et al. 2009). The NCEP FNL Operational Global Analysis data with a horizontal resolution of $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$, 27 vertical levels and temporal resolution of 6 hours, was used as meteorological initial and boundary conditions. The data are interpolated to the model grid using the WRF pre-processing system (WPS). The gas-phase chemistry model used in this study was the Regional Atmospheric Chemistry Mechanism (RACM; Stockwell et al. 1997). The aerosol module included the Modal Aerosol Dynamics Model for Europe (MADE Ackermann et al. 1998) for the inorganic fraction, and the Volatility Basis Set (VBS, Ahmadov et al. 2012) for the organic aerosols.

We run two simulations with the WRF-Chem model, which had different emission setups. The first simulation (BASE) included anthropogenic emissions from EMEP emission inventory (www.emep.int) (Kuenen et al. 2014) and biogenic emissions of isoprene calculated with the Guenther scheme. The second simulation additionally included the FINN fire emission inventory (Wiedinmyer et al. 2011).

2.4. Magnetic field, activity indices, and solar wind data

The interplanetary magnetic field (IMF), other provisional geomagnetic indices and solar wind data has been obtained from NASA/GSFC's Space Physics Data Facility's OMNIWeb (or CDAWeb or ftp) service. These are high resolution (1-min) OMNI Solar wind magnetic field data at Earth's Bow Shock Nose (BSN), also 1-min provisional activity indices data available at OMNIWeb: High-Resolution OMNI (https://omniweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/form/omni_min.html). The high-resolution OMNI data used

Figure 1. TEC (in blue), UB (in red) and LB (in green) during 12 (Figure 1A), 13 (Figure 1B), 14 (Figure 1C), 15 (Figure 1D) July, 2018, without forest fire during geomagnetic quiet condition; and 22 (Figure 1E), 23 (Figure 1F), 24 (Figure 1G), 25 (Figure 1H) July, 2018, during the forest fire event over Greece. TEC, UB and LB are in TECu where $1 \text{ TECu} = 10^{16} \text{ electrons/m}^2$.

in the this paper is combined with 1-min averaged ACE, Wind, IMP 8 and Geotail magnetic field and plasma data.

3. Results and discussion

We started by comparing the TEC fluctuation in the quiet geomagnetic days to the forest fire duration over the Greece. We have chosen 31 quiet geomagnetic days from June (5-6, 9-17, 20-22, 29-30 June 2018) and July (1-15 July 2018) 2018 during which the geomagnetic indices were $20 \text{ nT} > \text{Dst index} > -15 \text{ nT}$ (Joselyn 1989). We chose the data from the months of June and July as TEC data has seasonal dependence as well. This ensured that these days chosen were close to the month of forest fire. We have calculated the monthly median of the TEC data and defined upper boundary (UB) and lower boundary (LB) of the TEC data using the criteria suggested by Liu et al. (2004).

$$\text{UB (TECu)} = \text{MM} + 1.34\sigma \quad (2)$$

Figure 2. Solar wind and provisional activity indices during the wildfire occurrence, over Greece during 19-26 July, 2018. Figure 2 shows IMF B_x (blue) B_y (red) B_z (yellow); solar wind speed V (in Km/s); proton density D (in number per cm^3); temperature T (in Kelvin); wind pressure P (in nano Pascale); Electric Field E_y (in mV/m); and sym-H Dst index (nano Tesla).

$$LB \text{ (TECu)} = MM - 1.34\sigma \quad (3)$$

Where σ is the standard deviation of the TEC data and MM is the monthly median in TEC unit (TECu) i.e., $\text{TECu} = 10^{16} \text{el/m}^2$. The TEC data presented in Figure 1 is between $15\text{-}30^\circ$ in geographic longitude and $30\text{-}45^\circ$ N geographic latitude. The TEC data is averaged every 5 minutes. Figure 1(A–D) shows the TEC (in blue), UB (in red), and LB (in green) during (geomagnetically quiet day/without forest fire) 12-15 July 2018 respectively. Figure 1(E–H) shows the TEC (in blue), UB (in red), and LB (in green) during (forest fire). If we compare the figures at the left to the figures at the right, it is easy to observe that during the geomagnetic quiet days and the days without

forest fire, TEC data remains within the UB and LB limits. However, during the forest fire days, it is close to the UB and sometimes it exceeds the UB. [Figure 2](#) clearly shows that during the forest fire event, the geomagnetic conditions were quiet. Therefore, the TEC enhancements appear to be associated with the forest fire.

The wildfire event over Greece occurred during 19-26 July 2018. In this paper we are studying atmospheric-ionospheric signatures induced due to the forest fire. Therefore it is necessary to make it sure that all the ionospheric unusual signatures that we observe over the wild fire incidence sight are solely induced due to the wild fire only. We also need to be assured that there was absence of solar events during the forest fire duration. [Figure 2](#) shows the NASA OMNIWeb solar wind and provisional activity index related data. As it is evident in the [Figure 2](#) B_x , B_y and B_z fluctuations between ± 10 nT, and the Dst index was varying between 5 to -20 nT, wind speed was between 400-600 km/s, proton density, pressure, electric field and temperature data was within the usual limit of quiet to weak moderate solar activity conditions. This figure confirms that the solar activity condition was quiet and if we observe any ionospheric signature then the solar activity effect on them will be minimal during this period.

For a dynamic system such as ionosphere which varies on a time scale ranging from years to seconds and from several hundred kilometers to a few centimeter on spatial scale, it is hard to see the changes contributed from a very localized event such as forest fire, volcano, earthquake, etc. (Priyadarshi et al. 2018). Detrending is a very useful technique to study the plasma density contributed from such a local event. It removes the average variation (trend) from the data and brings out the fluctuations in the data caused due to local events.

Here we are presenting the detrended TEC data over Greece during a forest fire episode that occurred near Athens. We have observed some significant enhancements in the data before 22 July 2018 onward until 25 July 2018. We are interested in large scale atmospheric-ionospheric perturbations that have occurred over the forest fire episode zone. First, we will discuss the observations and results related to the detrended GPS TEC data and thereafter we will talk about the changes in atmospheric trace gases over Greece during the Forest Fire episodes that occurred during 22-25 July 2018.

[Figure 3](#) shows the detrended GPS TEC as well as three atmospheric parameters map over Greece (geographic latitude range $30-45^\circ$ N and geographic longitude range $15-30^\circ$ E). [Figure 3A](#) shows the detrended GPS TEC Map at 4:35 UT where we see a large scale detrended GPS TEC enhanced perturbation (in dotted rectangle) between $\sim 35-38^\circ$ N and $25-30^\circ$ E. This giant perturbation structure gradually grows and moves northward as evident from [Figure 3B](#) at 4:40 UT; and [Figure 3C](#) at 4:45 UT. It is growing more in the geographic latitudinal direction as compared to the geographic longitudinal direction. Another noticeable aspect is the lower geographic latitudinal boundary of this ionospheric detrended GPS TEC perturbation is almost constant at $\sim 35^\circ$ N; which means a source that is causing this perturbation is active at its origin and spreading with time in the northward geographic latitudinal direction. Further, this peculiar feature actuates us to infer that these perturbations are caused due to the forest fire episode that occurred over Greece in July 2018.

Figure 3. TEC fluctuation (in TECu) on 22 July 2018 over Greece. Here (A) shows Δ TEC at 04:35 UT; (B) at 04:40 UT; and (C) at 04:45 UT; (Map area under dotted line shows the moving TID structure). Atmospheric particulate matter and greenhouse gases detrended concentration over Greece on 22 July 2018 at 05:00 UT. PM_{10} (in $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$; Figure 3F), CO_2 (in ppmv; Figure 3D), and CH_4 (in ppmv; Figure 3E).

Following the data from the International Energy Agency (IEA), forest fires contribute 5-10% of the global CO_2 emission every year. Major emitted gases from the forest fires are CO_2 and other greenhouse gases. Forest fires also add particulate material in Earth's atmosphere. The CO_2 may cause long term global warming over the years. However, particulate materials may cause long term global warming as well

as short term cooling effect. Wildfires emit about ~ 8 billion tons of CO_2 every year (data from IEA).

The channel that transfers the energy evolved through forest fire to the ionosphere goes through the atmosphere. Therefore, if we see some changes in the ionosphere above the forest fire surface in Greece, there must be similar changes in the atmospheric gases and particulate materials right below or in the vicinity of the ionosphere in the atmosphere. We may observe some displacement in the location of enhanced concentration while energy transport from the atmosphere into the ionosphere.

We have also plotted 3 atmospheric parameters in Figure 3D, E and F that get influenced most during the forest fires episodes. PM_{10} in micro-gram per cubic meter ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), CO_2 , and CH_4 is expressed in the standard air pollutant concentrations units as ppmv (parts per million by volume). Figure 3 shows the atmospheric particulate matter and greenhouse gases detrended concentration over Greece on 22 July 2018 at 04:00 UT. Similar to the Figure 3A–C and Figure 7A detrended ΔTEC enhancement, we see enhanced concentration of detrended PM_{10} ($22\text{--}45 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$; Figure 3F); Figure 3D, CO_2 ($25\text{--}100$ ppmv), and CH_4 ($0.01\text{--}0.5$ ppmv; Figure 3E) between $25\text{--}30^\circ$ E geographic longitudes and $33\text{--}45^\circ$ geographic latitudes. The ground based GPS/GNSS receivers may catch different number of satellites in different time slots. Therefore, TEC observation presented is not uniform in all the portion of the map every time. In some regions it may be dense and in other it may have a few observations. The main objective of the presented paper is to find the ionospheric TEC fluctuations related to the forest fire. Therefore, we first investigate if there are TEC fluctuations associated to the forest fire. Once the TEC fluctuations are observed, thereafter we examine if these fluctuations are related to the simultaneously enhanced fluctuations in the atmospheric greenhouse gases and particulate matter. There are other regions in which we do see the enhancement in the atmospheric greenhouse gases as well as the particulate materials. But for the presented paper we are talking about only those geographic sectors where we have observed fluctuations in the ionospheric detrended TEC.

If observed closely, for Figures 3–6, the regions in the maps that has incoherence in TEC enhancement while having high Greenhouse gases density mostly have less dense TEC observations. But still these TEC values showed some small fluctuations. Besides this, our TEC data time resolution is one minute, however, we have greenhouse gases and particulate matter observation every one hour. Therefore, a small spatial shift in the greenhouse gases region should be accepted. On 23 July 2018, we have observed a giant perturbation structure during 2:20 UT to 2:50 UT over Greece (Figure 4). Initially, this perturbation structure is varying between $\sim 33\text{--}37^\circ$ N geographic latitudes and $\sim 15\text{--}20^\circ$ E geographic longitudes at 2:35 UT. After 10 minutes at 2:45 UT, its spreads are $\sim 32\text{--}42^\circ$ N geographic latitudes and $\sim 15\text{--}20^\circ$ E geographic longitudes (Figure 4B). Figure 4C shows the perturbation of the same structure spreading between $\sim 36\text{--}45^\circ$ N geographic latitudes and $\sim 15\text{--}20^\circ$ E geographic longitudes at 2:50 UT. At 2:50 UT the perturbation structure exists between $\sim 36\text{--}45^\circ$ N in geographic latitudes and $\sim 18\text{--}23^\circ$ E geographic longitudes. The detrended GPS TEC fluctuation structure is growing along the geographic latitude as well as along the geographic longitude. But, the first TEC fluctuation structure has a significantly

Figure 4. TEC fluctuation (in TECu) on 23 July 2018 over Greece. Here (A) shows Δ TEC at 02:35 UT; (B) at 02:45 UT; and (C) at 02:50 UT (Map area under dotted line shows the moving TID structure). Atmospheric particulate matter and greenhouse gases detrended concentration over Greece on 23 July 2018 at 02:00 UT. PM_{10} (in $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$; Figure 4F), CO_2 (in ppmv; Figure 4D), and CH_4 (in ppmv; Figure 4E).

higher intensity and it is growing with time along the latitude as well as longitude. Figure 4 (D–F) shows the atmospheric particulate material and greenhouse gases detrended concentration over Greece on 23 July 2018 at 02:00 UT. Alike detrended Δ TEC enhancement in Figure 4 (A–C) and Figure 7B, we see similar enhanced concentration of detrended PM_{10} ($18\text{--}22 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$; Figure 4C), CO_2 ($25\text{--}100$ ppmv; Figure 4D), and CH_4 ($0.01\text{--}0.5$ ppmv; Figure 4E) between $15\text{--}20^\circ$ E geographic longitudes

Figure 5. TEC fluctuation (in TECu) on 24 July 2018 over Greece. Here (A) shows Δ TEC at 18:40 UT; (B) at 19:00 UT; and (C) at 19:10 UT; (Map area under dotted line shows the moving TID structure). Atmospheric particulate matter and greenhouse gases detrended concentration over Greece on 24 July 2018 at 18:00 UT. PM_{10} (in $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$; Figure 5F), CO_2 (in ppmv; Figure 5D), and CH_4 (in ppmv; Figure 5E).

and 30–40° N geographic latitudes. Atmospheric gases and particulate material data are available only in hourly time resolution; consequently, we cannot show every 5 or 10 minutes changes in the atmospheric greenhouse gases and particulate materials.

Figure 5 show the GPS detrended TEC high-density structure expansion on 24 July 2018. At 18:40 between ~ 44 – 37° N geographic latitudes and 15– 20° E geographic longitudes. Figure 5A; at 18:40 between ~ 44 – 37° N geographic latitudes and 15– 20° E

geographic longitudes; **Figure 5B**, at 19:00 between $\sim 42\text{--}35^\circ$ N geographic latitudes and $15\text{--}20^\circ$ E geographic longitudes **Figure 5C**, at 19:10 between $\sim 41\text{--}32^\circ$ N geographic latitudes and $15\text{--}20^\circ$ E geographic longitudes. The perturbation structures shown in **Figure 5** are propagating in the north to the south latitudinal direction at constant geographic longitudes range between $15\text{--}20^\circ$ E. **Figure 5** also shows a feature of ionospheric perturbations caused due to the forest fire episode. **Figure 5 (D–F)** show the atmospheric particulate matter and greenhouse gases detrended concentration over Greece on 24 July 2018 at 18:00 UT. Similar to the **Figure 5 (A–C)** and **Figure 7C** detrended Δ TEC enhancement we see enhanced concentration of detrended PM_{10} ($18\text{--}22 \mu\text{g}; \text{kg}^{-1}$; please see **Figure 5F**), CO_2 ($25\text{--}100$ ppmv; please see **Figure 5D**), and CH_4 ($0.01\text{--}0.5$ ppmv; **Figure 5E**) between $15\text{--}20^\circ$ E geographic longitudes and $30\text{--}40^\circ$ N geographic latitudes.

On 25 May we have observed a medium-range detrended GPS TEC structure (**Figure 6**). There are many small scale high-density fluctuation structures but we are interested in almost constant density fluctuation giant structures only. We started to observe such a structure at 5:10 UT between $\sim 34\text{--}39^\circ$ N geographic latitudes and $15\text{--}22^\circ$ E geographic longitudes (**Figure 6A**); at 5:20 UT this structure moves a little in north latitudinal direction between $\sim 36\text{--}41^\circ$ N geographic latitudes and $15\text{--}22^\circ$ E geographic longitudes direction (**Figure 6B**). In **Figure 6C** at 5:40 UT between $\sim 38\text{--}45^\circ$ N geographic latitudes and $15\text{--}22^\circ$ E geographic longitudes direction. Overall this high-density detrended GPS TEC fluctuation is moving in the northern latitudinal direction and at merely constant geographic longitude. **Figure 6 (D–F)** show the atmospheric particulate matter and greenhouse gases detrended concentration over Greece on 25 July 2018 at 05:00 UT. Similar to the **Figure 6 (A–C)**; and **Figure 7D** detrended Δ TEC enhancement we see enhanced concentration of detrended PM_{10} ($18\text{--}22 \mu\text{g}; \text{kg}^{-1}$; please see **Figure 6F**), CO_2 ($25\text{--}100$ ppmv; please see **Figure 6D**), and CH_4 ($0.01\text{--}0.5$ ppmv; **Figure 6C**) between $15\text{--}22^\circ$ E geographic longitude and $30\text{--}40^\circ$ N geographic latitude.

To check the diurnal variation of the high density detrended GPS TEC fluctuation between 22–25 July 2019 we have plotted them as a subplot (**Figure 7**) in geographic latitude at y-axis and universal time (UT) hours at the x-axis at a constant and narrow latitude range as discussed in **Figures 2–5**. **Figure 7** has been prepared by averaging the detrended GPS TEC data in bins where the bin resolution is 2° in geographic latitude and 5 minutes in UT. In **Figure 7A** we see several constant density perturbations from 2–7 UT between $30\text{--}40^\circ$ N geographic latitude at a constant geographic longitude range of $24\text{--}25^\circ$ E. In **Figure 7B**, we observe around 3 constant density perturbations existing during 2–9 UT between $30\text{--}40^\circ$ N geographic latitude at a constant geographic longitude range of $17\text{--}22^\circ$ E. **Figure 7C** shows only one constant density perturbation existing during 16–23 UT between $30\text{--}40^\circ$ N geographic latitude at a constant geographic longitude range of $15\text{--}20^\circ$ E and in the last **Figure 7D**; nearly three constant density perturbations existing during 0–8 UT between $30\text{--}40^\circ$ N geographic latitude at a constant geographic longitude range of $16\text{--}20^\circ$ E. These perturbation structures have generated at certain geographic latitude range and with time they have evolved in geographic latitudinal direction at a narrow longitude strip. Their constant density fluctuations indicate that this high density detrended GPS TEC fluctuation strips are triggered from only one source.

Figure 6. TEC fluctuation (in TECu) on 25 July 2018 over Greece. Here (A) shows Δ TEC at 05:10 UT; (B) at 05:30 UT; and (C) at 05:40 UT; (Map area under dotted line shows the moving TID structure). Atmospheric particulate matter and greenhouse gases detrended concentration over Greece on 25 July 2018 at 05:00 UT. PM₁₀ (in $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$; Figure 6F), CO₂ (in ppmv; Figure 6D), and CH₄ (in ppmv; Figure 6E).

Figure 8 shows diurnal variation of the detrended TEC (Figure 8a), detrended PM₁₀ & PM_{2.5} (Figure 8b), detrended CO₂ (Figure 8c), detrended NO₂ (Figure 8d), detrended SO₂ (Figure 8e) and detrended CH₄ (Figure 8f). The data plotted in Figure 8 has been chosen between 30-45° geographic latitude and 15-30° geographic

Figure 7. Detrended TEC maps (in TECu) over Greece. Here (A) shows the map for 22 July 2018; (B) 23 July 2018; (C) 24 July 2018, and (D) 25 July 2018 (Map area under dotted line shows the equivalent area and time of the moving TID structure shown in Figures 3–6).

Figure 8. 22 July 2019 (a) detrended TEC, (b) detrended PM_{10} & $PM_{2.5}$, (c) detrended CO_2 , (d) detrended NO_2 , (e) detrended SO_2 and (f) detrended CH_4 .

longitude (over Greece) as on 22 July 2018. This figure shows the actual connection between forest fire-induced atmospheric and ionospheric fluctuations. Detrending allows us to visualize the external contribution by removing the background effect. These fluctuations can be either with positive numerical values or with the negative numerical values. We have obtained a similar variation trend during the entire forest fire episode (20-25 July 2019). However, the particulate matter is shown in Figure 8b and NO_2 shown in Figure 8d shows gradual enhancement between $\sim 5:00$ UT to $\sim 6:00$ UT. Overall diurnal variation of the atmospheric parameters shown between Figure 8 b-f is identical with the detrended ionospheric TEC (Figure 8a) with a little time delay. These trends allow us to infer that the energy channel passing from the forest fire-affected regions to the ionosphere through the atmosphere, first causes fluctuations in the atmosphere and thereafter to the ionosphere.

Table 1 shows the concentration of the different atmospheric gases during 20-25 July 2019.

Figure 9 shows the daily emission of the different atmospheric gases during 20-25 July 2018. From the Table 1 and Figure 9 it is evident that concentration of atmospheric gases and aerosol started significant enhancement since 22 July 2018. However the variation trend in aerosol and atmospheric greenhouse gases are alike. Among all the provided data during 22-25 July 2018, maximum atmospheric gases and aerosol concentration has been observed on 23 July 2018, however concentrations on 22, 24 and 25 July 2018 were in the close variation ranges.

Table 1. Emission concentration in mega-gram/day.

dates	PM _{2.5}	PM ₁₀	CO ₂	NO ₂	SO ₂	CH ₄
20/07/2018	5.057564	6.432681	33560.54	69.00554	6.324772	192.7111
21/07/2018	0.395414	0.522092	2815.185	5.092788	0.548671	6.8477
22/07/2018	2.539377	3.352918	18079.34	32.70629	3.52361	43.97646
23/07/2018	7.052367	8.535795	42464.83	103.0669	7.592415	454.8349
24/07/2018	3.304809	4.244473	22340.1	44.4427	4.249056	108.2984
25/07/2018	2.744754	3.624092	19541.53	35.35146	3.808588	47.53314

4. Summary and conclusions

Geological natural hazards such as earthquakes and tsunami triggered atmospheric as well as ionospheric anomalies have been studied extensively. The mechanism that is believed to transport anomalies from Earth's surface to the upper atmosphere is the gravity waves. Gravity waves are generated at the interface of two medium such as ocean and air, or ground and air, during the incidence of natural hazards when the surface of the ocean and/or the ground moves. As a consequence of such surface movements gravity waves come into the existence and it intensify due to the changes in density and temperature of radon gases in the lower atmosphere (Dobrovolsky et al. 1979; Pulinets 1998; Planini et al. 2004; Priyadarshi et al. 2011a, 2011b and references therein). Forest fire smoke detection and dynamics in the stratosphere were hot investigation topics for the past few decades. However, no attempts have been made yet to sense the forest fire signature in the ionosphere. A very devastating forest fire event had occurred in Greece during 20–25 July 2018. Joint investigation of the atmospheric trace gases, particulate matter, and ionospheric TEC shows the forest fire induced fluctuations occur in the atmospheric components, which are present at different heights from Earth's surface. We have detrended all the atmospheric and ionospheric data to remove the background contribution. It helped us to see real-time fluctuation in the atmospheric and ionospheric parameters density. In the ionosphere, we have observed several large scales detrended TEC fluctuation structures and similar fluctuations in the atmospheric gases (CO₂, NO₂, SO₂, and CH₄) as well as in particulate matter PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} have been observed. We observed some small special shifts in the structures of density fluctuation between atmospheric greenhouse gases/particulate matter and ionospheric TEC.

The ionospheric electron density fluctuations during the geological natural hazards originally appear from the troposphere. The troposphere temperature rises due to the ejection of hot material or greenhouse gases from Earth's surface during the natural hazards (in our case the forest fire). Due to this, impedance of the lower atmosphere decreases and it gives rise to internal atmospheric gravity waves. (e.g., Dobrovolsky et al. 1979; Pulinets 1998). There are strong experimental evidences in the previous research works (e.g., Pancheva and Mukhtarov 2011 and references therein, Priyadarshi et al. 2011a, 2011b and references therein) that confirmed that the sudden atmospheric layers warming results in the diurnal behaviors of the greenhouse gases, particulate matter, mean ionospheric electron density, as well as GPS TEC. Pulinets 1998 presented that at the height of about 60 km from Earth's surface the strong and large scale vertical electric field (ca 1000 Vm⁻¹) appears in the anisotropic atmospheric conductive layer during the geological natural hazards. This vertical electric

Figure 9. Histogram showing the emission over Greece in Mg (10^6 gram/day) between 20–25 July 2019 of (a) PM_{10} ; (b) $PM_{2.5}$; (c) CO_2 ; (d) CH_4 ; (e) NO_2 ; and (d) SO_2 .

field can penetrate in the ionosphere over the hazardous regions and create anomalies in the ionospheric electron density. Chen et al. 1999 presented that the electric field generated due to natural hazards or atmospheric warming start to penetrate in the Earth's ionosphere when its spatial scale is equivalent to the height of the ionosphere ~ 100 km.

In summary, the presented paper discusses a devastating forest fire event that occurred in July 2018 in Greece. We have observed fluctuations in the atmospheric greenhouse gases and particulate matter. The atmospheric fluctuations are also found in the conjugate vicinity to the ionospheric irregularity fluctuations. Ionospheric detrended TEC structures have a little spatial and temporal shift than the atmospheric fluctuations triggered due to the forest fire. In future we will focus on more such events and perform statistics to study the degree of ionospheric TEC fluctuations and greenhouse gases associated to the forest fire events occurring in dissimilar seasons as well as geographic locations.

Data availability statement

We have used GPS TEC data from openly available Madrigal database (<http://madrigal.igccas.ac.cn/madrigal/>) as well as from WRF-Chem (<https://www2.aom.ucar.edu/wrf-chem>), which is openly available and it has provided spatial and temporal distribution of air pollutants over Greece. The geomagnetic indices and IMF data are

available on NASA/GSFC's Space Physics Data Facility's OMNIWeb (or CDAWeb or ftp) service, and OMNI data (https://omniweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/form/omni_min.html).

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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